

Evaluating the Level of Cybersecurity Literacy among Undergraduates in Nepal

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Abstract

As Nepal's higher education system shifts toward digitalization, the importance of cybersecurity literacy among bachelor's students has never been greater. With increasing threats like phishing, scams, and data breaches, it is crucial to assess how well students are prepared to protect themselves in this digital environment. Improving cybersecurity literacy in higher education can play a vital role in preparing students for a secure digital future and reducing exposure to digital threats, scams, and risks.

Our study aims to examine the cybersecurity awareness level among bachelor's students in Nepal. Understanding their knowledge, attitudes, and daily practices is our main goal. We used a quantitative survey method to collect data from 210 participants because this approach is inexpensive, less time-consuming, and effective in understanding students' opinions and experiences regarding digital threats, their efforts to mitigate them, and how cybersecurity education impacts their online lives. Descriptive statistics are used to analyze the data, along with a binary logistic regression model.

The findings reveal a significant gap in cybersecurity literacy, the spread of vulnerabilities, and the limited impact of current training efforts. The study also shows no link between cybersecurity awareness and gender. Additionally, the results indicate how students recognize common cyberattacks, manage risks, and evaluate the effectiveness of current cybersecurity education. By analyzing key factors influencing cybersecurity awareness, this research provides valuable insights for universities, policymakers, and cybersecurity professionals.

Keywords: *bachelor's degree students, cybersecurity awareness, cybersecurity literacy, digital threats, digitalization*